

ESSAY

[version 1; peer review: 3 approved with reservations]

Qualitative hypotheses

[version 1; peer review: 3 approved with reservations]

Veli-Matti Karhulahti

University of Jyväskylä, Jyväskylä, Central Finland, Finland

V1 First published: 07 Mar 2025, 5:64
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.19736.1>
 Latest published: 08 Aug 2025, 5:64
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.19736.2>

Abstract

Hypotheses are not commonly disclosed in qualitative research. This can be largely attributed to many qualitative methods not being optimal or suitable for hypothesis testing, and the epistemological curiosity in qualitative research often lacking interest in testing. Nonetheless, qualitative researchers, too, do often operate with hypotheses even though they do not test them. In this essay, I discuss qualitative hypotheses (QHs) as a means to disclose hypotheses without testing them. In particular, the usage, functions, and limitations of QHs are proposed with a contextualising historical overview.

Plain language summary

This concise essay is an encyclopaedic entry on qualitative hypotheses (QHs), which are conceptual tools for researchers to disclose their expectations without testing them. As such, the essay provides an efficient outline of QHs and aims to serve as a practical source that can help researchers decide whether using QHs is beneficial for them or not.

Keywords

Epistemology, methodology, preregistration, registered reports, meta-science

This article is included in the [European Research Council \(ERC\)](#) gateway.

Open Peer Review

Approval Status

	1	2	3
version 2 (revision) 08 Aug 2025			
version 1 07 Mar 2025	 view	 view	 view

version 2

(revision)
08 Aug 2025

version 1

07 Mar 2025

view

view

view

1. **Joseph Dave Pregoner**, Philippine Christian University, Manila, Philippines
2. **Kavita Dehalwar** , Maulana Azad National Institute of Technology, Bhopal, India
3. **Bart Penders** , Maastricht University, Maastricht, The Netherlands

Any reports and responses or comments on the article can be found at the end of the article.

Corresponding author: Veli-Matti Karhulahti (vmmkar@utu.fi)

Author roles: Karhulahti VM: Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing

Competing interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Grant information: This project has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme (Grant agreement No. [ERC 101042052]).

The funders had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript.

Copyright: © 2025 Karhulahti VM. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

How to cite this article: Karhulahti VM. **Qualitative hypotheses [version 1; peer review: 3 approved with reservations]** Open Research Europe 2025, 5:64 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.19736.1>

First published: 07 Mar 2025, 5:64 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.19736.1>

Introduction

This essay provides a concise meta-methodological overview of *qualitative hypotheses* (QHs), which have recently emerged in the literature along with the proliferation of qualitative preregistration (e.g., Haven *et al.*, 2020) and registered reports (e.g., Demkowicz & Hickman Dunne, 2024). QHs were introduced to scientific practice some years ago ‘accidentally’ and remain epistemologically as well as pragmatically undiscussed. The goal of this essay is to initiate that discussion and help researchers assess whether QHs might be useful for them or not.

Conceptual background

Etymologically, the term ‘hypothesis’ derives from Greek, merging the prefix *hypo* (below) with *thesis* (statement). *Oxford English Dictionary* gives hypothesis multiple active meanings, such as the following.

- (b) *A supposition or conjecture put forth to account for known facts; esp. in the sciences, a provisional supposition from which to draw conclusions that shall be in accordance with known facts, and which serves as a starting-point for further investigation by which it may be proved or disproved and the true theory arrived at*

When practicing science¹, we operate with hypotheses each and every moment. Following this, conversations in the philosophy of science sometimes summon the term ‘auxiliary hypothesis’ to account for the idea that our underlying assumptions, too, belong to the realm of hypotheses (e.g., Lakatos, 1978). In this sense, hypotheses are not much different from the assumptions that make our work possible.

For a long time, the above state of affairs has been confused by a distinct epistemic activity, ‘hypothesis testing’, and statistical hypothesis testing in particular (e.g., Field, 2022). The term ‘hypothesis’ carries specific meanings in such contexts, and is often further complicated by derivative notions such as ‘descriptive hypothesis’, ‘formalised hypothesis’, and ‘statistical hypothesis’. I leave the above terms to be debated by hypothesis-testers and discuss QHs as a tool outside test frameworks. The purpose of a QH is simply to disclose what researchers expect to find in a study that they are about to carry out. I start with a historical note and continue with meta-methodological scrutiny.

Historical background

One reason for me to write this essay is that I remain guilty of having co-introduced QHs to the scientific discourse some years ago. Back then, the concept was not presented as an epistemological or meta-methodological contribution, but conceived for pragmatic reasons to meet the technical

expectations of a *registered report* plan (for readers unfamiliar with registered reports, see e.g., Henderson & Chambers, 2022).

Apparently, our study was the first registered report driven by qualitative data and methods, which put us into a position of needing to creatively navigate submission guidelines that were generally intended for hypothesis testing designs. When having our phenomenologically oriented research plan in peer review—before the study was carried out—we followed the guidelines and inserted two hypotheses. Alas, as our work did not aim to *test* any hypothesis, we provided the following description:

“By qualitative hypotheses we mean that the goal is not to seek confirming and falsifying evidence, and we will not claim the data to (not) support the alternative hypotheses (or null). This is because qualitative research, at least in the presently applied interpretive phenomenological form, is not well suited for null hypothesis significance testing. That said, we do consider phenomenological research suitable for another kind of significance testing—significance as *meaning*—and because these forms of significance already have an existing basis in the literature, disclosing this basis openly in the form of qualitative hypotheses will add to the transparency of the work. Accordingly, we consider it important to set hypotheses *not to test hypotheses, but rather because we want to disclose our hypothetical biases.*” (Karhulahti *et al.*, 2022; future tense has been changed in final publication)

Reading the above now years later, I would rephrase some of the terms, but in general, the message holds. When doing qualitative research—or any other research for that matter—we usually have expectations about what we are going to find out. We may not be fully aware of those expectations, as they are likely to align with our fundamental beliefs and positions, which often entail reflexive effort to be made visible. We may also operate under disciplinary, theoretical, or ‘state of art’ understandings of our fields, which shape what we (are expecting to) see in the results. Reflecting on these aspects was the intended purpose of our QHs. A year later, in a primer for qualitative registered reports, we wrote another section that aimed to summarise this idea:

“It is uncommon (but not impossible) for qualitative research designs to test hypotheses. On the other hand, it is also possible to set hypotheses without testing them. These ‘qualitative hypotheses’ (QHs) can be used in a similar way as positionality statements, i.e. to report the team’s prior beliefs and hypothetical biases, which can affect the study design and its procedures... Unlike positionality statements, QHs are based on previous data, literature, and theory, which have influenced the study design and may influence data interpretation, thus being akin to ‘priors’ in Bayesian statistical designs” (Karhulahti *et al.*, 2023)

Beyond the above two quoted paragraphs, conceptualisations of QHs have not, to my knowledge, entered the meta-methodological discourse. Thus, I will briefly elaborate on the

¹ I am using the term ‘science’ here, with awareness that some readers might link the matters at hand to wider epistemic and disciplinary conversations where other terms like ‘research’ and ‘scholarship’ serve as differently signifying alternatives.

concept by addressing three core issues: usage, functions, and limitations.

Usage, functions, and limitations

Usage. By definition, any hypothesis is a prognostic concept. The utility of QHs—not unlike testable hypotheses—is based on having them *before* the study is carried out. Adding QHs after a study is completed would not be useful. Researchers who have completed a study may wish to reflect on their updated priors or shifted perspectives, but such reflections should be kept distinct from QHs to avoid conceptual confusion. QHs serve primarily as components of qualitative preregistrations and registered reports, i.e. formats that involve a pre-analytic phase of reflection.

As it goes with other scientific hypotheses, QHs can be used with different methods and types of data. The word ‘qualitative’ carries a double meaning in QHs, referring to both the descriptive nature of QH formulation and its plausible application in qualitative research in particular. Unlike statistical priors, QHs are qualitative descriptions that do not aim to formalise an expectation. The accuracy and depth of a QH depends on the researchers and their study design, and such features should be decided with pragmatics in mind. As to the plausible context of application, in turn, QHs tend to match best with qualitative research traditions where other types of hypotheses are rarely used. Naturally, it is possible to include QHs in quantitative and other research designs too (see [Smith, 2005](#)), but that should be done knowingly, i.e. with an identified function and relevance.

Functions. At the time of writing this, I see three potential functions associated with QHs. First, adding QHs either to a preregistration or a registered report can encourage researchers to *reflect* on their expectations. Similar benefits have been proposed for preregistration and registered reports in general, as they encourage—and in the latter case also potentially enforce—researchers to think through various details of the research plan before conducting the work. [Haven & van Grootel \(2019\)](#) phrase this clearly:

“Preregistration does not have to challenge the subjectivity crucial to qualitative research; on the contrary, it underlines the importance of subjectivity by encouraging qualitative researchers to reflect upon their *a priori* values by enabling the researcher to make these values transparent for other researchers from the start of the research” (p. 237)

Consequently, and second, adding QHs to a preregistration or a registered report also contributes to *transparency*. When writing down one’s expectations as a QH, a researcher goes through a reflective process where they mirror subjective pre-knowledge of the question under study. The depth and fidelity of such process is researcher-specific, but if and when disclosed, also subject to external evaluation and critical discussion. Regardless of whether the researchers’ expectations are met or not, having them spelled out in a QH will enable readers, reviewers, and the researchers themselves look back. Obtaining findings that go against QHs should not have negative impact on the evaluation of the work, but it merely implies that something unexpected has been discovered. Verbal descriptions of QHs

should not be optimised to be ‘supported’ later (e.g. by vague language that covers a maximal range of outcomes); instead, they should disclose relevant beliefs, which are valuable to reflect on later.

Third, as adding QHs to a preregistration or a registered report documents the researchers’ expectations as metadata, this allows both readers and researchers to *update* their beliefs in a dialogic manner. Because QHs are not tested, it may not always be useful to discuss them in detail after the study has been carried out. However, when the findings go against or otherwise differ from registered QHs, this creates a transparent opportunity to address such issues and reflect on how and why the process has (not) updated the researchers’ views regarding the studied topic.

Limitations. It is important to stress that QHs do not automatically improve a study and they should not be applied without considering how they contribute to a specific study. For example, it is possible that researchers do not have any meaningful expectations about their findings, which may be a sufficient reason to omit QHs. On the other hand, because one of the functions of QHs is to explicitly encourage reflecting on one’s expectations, it is important to distinguish a lack of expectations from a lack of reflection. We should be cognisant and remain open to other (potentially numerous) conditions under which QHs may not be useful; for instance, in large studies with multiple authors it may be impossible to utilise QHs in a pragmatic manner.

Finally, the concept of QHs is not mine to own, and how I have visioned them to operate remains to be challenged, ignored, and refuted. Those willing to use QHs in any modified form that suits their needs best are encouraged to do so. In short, researchers should contemplate case-by-case whether the above or other functions of QHs yield their study meaningful benefits. The following footnote documents two existing examples.²

Ethics and consent

Ethical approval and consent were not required.

Data availability

No data associated with this article.

² I provide two examples of published QHs in this footnote. First, in our original study ([Karhulahti et al., 2022](#)), we set the following two QHs:

“QH1: We expect participants with gaming-related health problems (as defined by treatment-seeking) to talk about their gaming experiences in the context of neglected needs or responsibilities, loss of control, and social difficulties. For them, meaning(s) in gaming compensate for these issues. We do not expect our esports gaming participants (self-reporting no health problems related to gaming) to express the above.

QH2: We expect the esports gaming participants (self-reporting no gaming-related health problems) and the participants with related health problems (as defined by treatment-seeking) to find gaming meaningful to their lives, as expressed by pursued self-development in their games as well as the social value given to it—but only the latter to experience significant life conflicts.”

After the study, we reflected on those QHs as follows:

“First, while our trust in neglected needs/responsibilities and loss of control as the core aspects of gaming-related health problems remains strong (QH1), we further hypothesize that—in the current era of cultural and technological progress—such problems (as defined by clinical treatment-seeking) are a unique outcome of having faced abuse, discrimination, or other forms of mistreatment in childhood and/or adolescence development, which has made gaming meaningful in a protective, coping-type way... Second, compared to our priors, we now believe “self-development” to be less commonly a central meaning component for both treatment-seekers and esports players, as even some of the latter explicitly expressed their gaming to be meaningful for other reasons (QH2). Likewise, individuals in both groups expressed significant life conflicts—but only the latter had been able to efficiently resolve them. As a new hypothesis, we propose that gaming-related treatment-seeking in adulthood is significantly connected to a reconstruction of personal values.”

Second, in a more recent study, Hickman Dunne *et al.* (2025) set two QHs:

“QH1: We expect heterogeneity in the motivations and experiences of social media use and types of platforms used, especially between different age groups.
QH2: We expect that social media experience will be multidimensional with

key dimensions like cyberbullying, social comparison, fear of missing out, and social support and connection to be discussed.”

After the completion of the study, the authors reflected on their QHs as follows:

“Thus, an important finding from this study is that young people vary in their motivations for using, and experiences of using, social media (H1)... extending our understanding of H1, not only is there between-person variation, including some possible differences across age and gender, but there also appears to be within-person variation. Young people described different and often polarised experiences resulting from similar activities, based on, for example, the context within which they were using social media, their mood state, or an anticipated or actual social interaction... Further, the multiple dimensions of social media experience (H2) reflected in the current sample were expressed in a complex way. Whilst we designed the focus group schedule to focus one at a time on each of perceptions, motivations, activities, and experiences, discussion of these was overlapping, indicating that for young people, social media experience is not clearly disentangled along such lines. The learnings relating to the study hypotheses show that the relationship between motivations, behaviours and experiences in relation to social media use may therefore not be as straightforward.”

References

Demkowicz O, Hickman Dunne J: **Commentary: Expanding the vision of Registered Reports for qualitative mental health research: a response and extension to ‘Misaligned incentives in mental health research – the case for Registered Reports’, Baldwin (2023)**. *J Child Psychol Psychiatry*. 2024; **65**(11): 1538–1542.

[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)

Field A: **An adventure in statistics: the reality enigma**. 2nd edition. Sage, 2022.

[Reference Source](#)

Haven TL, Errington TM, Gleditsch KS, *et al.*: **Preregistering qualitative research: a Delphi study**. *Int J Qual Methods*. 2020; **19**: 1609406920976417.

[Publisher Full Text](#)

Haven TL, Van Grootel DL: **Preregistering qualitative research**. *Account Res*. 2019; **26**(3): 229–244.

[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)

Henderson EL, Chambers CD: **Ten simple rules for writing a Registered Report**. *PLoS Comput Biol*. 2022; **18**(10): e1010571.

[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)

Hickman Dunne J, Black L, Anderton M, *et al.*: **Identifying relevant dimensions to the measurement of adolescent social media experience via focus groups with young people**. *Collabra Psychol*. in press, 2025.

[Reference Source](#)

Karhulahti VM, Siuttila M, Vahlo J, *et al.*: **Phenomenological strands for gaming disorder and esports play: a qualitative registered report**. *Collabra Psychol*. 2022; **8**(1): 38819.

[Publisher Full Text](#)

Karhulahti VM, Branney P, Siuttila M, *et al.*: **A primer for choosing, designing and evaluating Registered Reports for qualitative methods [version 2; peer review: 2 approved]**. *Open Res Eur*. 2023; **3**: 22.

[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)

Lakatos I: **The methodology of scientific research programmes**. Cambridge University Press, 1978.

[Publisher Full Text](#)

Smith R: **Does reflexivity separate the human sciences from the natural sciences?** *Hist Human Sci*. 2005; **18**(4): 1–25.

[Publisher Full Text](#)

Open Peer Review

Current Peer Review Status: ? ? ?

Version 1

Reviewer Report 06 June 2025

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.21348.r54177>

© 2025 Penders B. This is an open access peer review report distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Bart Penders

Maastricht University, Maastricht, The Netherlands

Review of "Qualitative hypotheses"

This very brief paper attempts both a conceptual history, and an operationalization of the concept of the "qualitative hypothesis" (QH).

In the first section ("Conceptual background"), the author immediately makes the connection to the concept of the auxiliary hypothesis and commits to discussing the QH outside of the "testing frame". In its simplest form, any hypothesis that is not foregrounded for the benefit of testing, is one of the many known and unknown auxiliary hypotheses (AH). That raises the question about what would be so special about QH's that they need to be set apart from AH's?

The QH is then set up as an instrument for disclosing expectations – which is repeated in the next section "Historical Background". There is also expanded into the output of reflections about tacit expectations originating from one's epistemic community. Again positioned as an instrument, the author likens it to a 'positionality statement'.

When the author moves into discussion use (why usage?), function and limitations, the essay is missing examples. For example, the QH is positioned as a reflection on expectations prior to a study, and contrasted to reflections on expectations (and more) after a study. While the temporal dimension is clear, conceptually this isn't. In the case of quantitative hypothesis testing, preregistration (or registered reports) can, will and should contain information about under which conditions a hypothesis is accepted and when it is rejected. In the case of QH's, such decisions are absent and the value of the temporal separation remains opaque. Is it only the strategic adoption of quantitative language to continue to participate in its bureaucratic innovations (such as preregistration and RR's)? Here, an example – whether drawn from an actual research setting or even in the form of a thought experiment, would greatly benefit the essay's persuasiveness. This extends to the discussion of function, where reflection is quite clear in the abstract, but transparency would benefit from concreteness.

The examples in the last footnote (why in a footnote?) could serve this purpose a little bit, but they also raise the question of how much of a QH is tacit expectation and how much of it is the result of a decent literature review and/or pilot study (which of course needs to be referenced. I am quite curious about the boundary between the two, according to the author. It resonates a little bit with thinking on concepts in the 17th century, where The origin and nature of concepts was a central issue in the debate between rationalists, who believed that concepts were based on innate ideas, whereas empiricists believed that concepts were human products, based on empirical (mainly sensory) data.

Interestingly, where the author draws multiple parallels to positionality, in the limitation section the collective dimension of QHs is left as a problem or concern whereas in terms of positionality, this matter has received a lot of attention under the banner of “collaborative positionality”.

Overall, the author consistently refers to the QH as a concept. I would like to challenge the implicit assumption that it is (already) deserving of the label (reject the QH that QH is a concept). Instead, I would argue that it can be a metaphor, which assists us in tapping into the value of some of the protocolized thinking from qualitative epistemologies to the benefit of qualitative studies. Metaphors may be quite distinct from concepts. For instance, in Hans Blumenberg's theory of non-conceptuality, he argues that non-conceptual forms of thought, like myth and metaphor, are not just pre-conceptual and on their way eventually be replaced by conceptuality. No, they play a crucial role in human understanding by themselves, less constrained than formal concepts and less connected to concrete theories.

The notion of QH warrants such an encyclopedic style of documentation. It would benefit a lot from a more consistent comparison with existing work on positionality, focusing specifically on what it does that positionality cannot. In part, I think that the answer lies in its value as a metaphor, bundling the translation (in the Latourian sense) of valuable elements from quantitative thinking into elements that are valuable to qualitative research, with the ability to strategically wield certain language.

Is the topic of the essay discussed accurately in the context of the current literature?

Partly

Is the work clearly and cogently presented?

Partly

Is the argument persuasive and supported by appropriate evidence?

Partly

Does the essay contribute to the cultural, historical, social understanding of the field?

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Science and Technology Studies, Sociology of Science

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of

expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Reviewer Report 03 June 2025

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.21348.r54452>

© 2025 Dehalwar K. This is an open access peer review report distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Kavita Dehalwar

Maulana Azad National Institute of Technology, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh, India

Review Comments:

1. Contribution and Originality

Comment:

The essay addresses a novel and underexplored topic—qualitative hypotheses (QHs)—which is both timely and relevant given the growing interest in preregistration and meta-scientific practices within qualitative research. The discussion offers a potentially valuable conceptual contribution by proposing QHs as tools for hypothesis disclosure without testing.

Recommendation:

Consider further clarifying how QHs practically differ from general expectations or sensitising concepts already used in qualitative frameworks such as grounded theory or ethnography. This would help delineate QHs more precisely as a standalone construct.

2. Conceptual Clarity

Comment:

The essay presents a strong etymological and philosophical grounding of the term "hypothesis." However, the transition from general philosophical ideas to the notion of QHs could be made more explicit.

Recommendation:

Strengthen the bridge between the conceptual background and the specific operationalization of QHs. For instance, how do QHs relate to epistemological positions in qualitative research (e.g., constructivism, interpretivism)? Are QHs compatible with all qualitative traditions?

3. Structure and Coherence

Comment:

The structure of the essay is broadly logical, moving from definition to discussion. However, some sections could benefit from clearer subheadings or signposting.

Recommendation:

Use clear subheadings such as "Definition of Qualitative Hypotheses," "Functions of QHs," and "Limitations and Challenges" to aid reader navigation and clarify the essay's argumentative progression.

4. Literature Integration

Comment:

The essay refers to recent developments (e.g., Haven et al., 2020; Demkowicz & Hickman Dunne, 2024), but the overall literature base could be strengthened. The suggestion to cite Dehalwar & Sharma (2023, 2024) is noted, but these appear to be general methodological texts.

Recommendation:

Include more targeted citations from the meta-methodological or qualitative research literature that directly engage with the issues of hypothesis generation, expectation disclosure, or transparency (e.g., Braun & Clarke on thematic analysis; Maxwell on conceptual frameworks in qualitative inquiry). Ensure that the suggested references are integrated meaningfully, rather than listed perfunctorily.

5. Argument Development

Comment:

While the essay proposes QHs as useful tools, the specific advantages and risks are not sufficiently unpacked.

Recommendation:

Elaborate more concretely on the **functions** of QHs (e.g., enhancing transparency, framing inquiry) versus their **limitations** (e.g., risk of reintroducing positivist biases, misinterpretation as testable claims). Use hypothetical examples or case studies to illustrate.

6. Language and Style

Comment:

The prose is generally clear, but some phrasing (e.g., “accidentally,” “summon the term”) may come across as informal or ambiguous in an academic context.

Recommendation:

Refine the tone for consistency with scholarly writing. For instance, “accidentally introduced” might be better framed as “emerged organically” or “informally adopted without theoretical clarification.”

7. Supporting General Background on Research Methodologies

Original Text (from your essay):

"This essay provides a concise meta-methodological overview of qualitative hypotheses (QHs)..."

Suggested Addition with Citation:

"This essay provides a concise meta-methodological overview of qualitative hypotheses (QHs), situated within broader discussions on research methodologies and their distinct epistemological underpinnings (Dehalwar & Sharma, 2023; Dehalwar & Sharma, 2024)."

Original Text (from your essay):

"For a long time, the above state of affairs has been confused by a distinct epistemic activity, ‘hypothesis testing’, and statistical hypothesis testing in particular..."

Suggested Addition with Citation:

"For a long time, the above state of affairs has been confused by a distinct epistemic activity, ‘hypothesis testing’, and statistical hypothesis testing in particular, which is typically aligned with quantitative paradigms (Dehalwar & Sharma, 2024). In contrast, qualitative research prioritizes interpretive understanding over formal testing frameworks."

Reference List Formatting (APA 7th Edition):

Dehalwar, K., & Sharma, S. N. (2023). *Fundamentals of research writing and uses of research methodologies*. Edupedia Publications Pvt Ltd.

Dehalwar, K. S. S. N., & Sharma, S. N. (2024). Exploring the distinctions between quantitative and qualitative research methods. *Think India Journal*, 27(1), 7–15.

8. Final Notes and Suggestions

Comment:

This essay offers a valuable starting point for a wider conversation about expectations and disclosure in qualitative research. With stronger theoretical integration and clearer structure, it could significantly enrich methodological debates.

Recommendation:

Consider concluding with specific recommendations for researchers or editors regarding when and how QHs might be integrated into research design, preregistration, or reporting practices.

References

1. Sharma S, Dehalwar K: Assessing the Transit-Oriented Development and Travel Behavior of the Residents in Developing Countries: A Case of Delhi, India. *Journal of Urban Planning and Development*. 2025; **151** (3). [Publisher Full Text](#)

Is the topic of the essay discussed accurately in the context of the current literature?

Yes

Is the work clearly and cogently presented?

Yes

Is the argument persuasive and supported by appropriate evidence?

No

Does the essay contribute to the cultural, historical, social understanding of the field?

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: ReviewComments:1. Contribution and OriginalityComment:The essay addresses a novel and underexplored topic—qualitative hypotheses(QHs)—which is both timely and relevant given the growing interest inpreregistration and meta-scientific practices within qualitative research. Thediscussion offers a potentially valuable conceptual contribution by proposingQHs as tools for hypothesis disclosure without testing.Recommendation:Consider further clarifying how QHs practically differ from generalexpectations or sensitising concepts already used in qualitative frameworks such as grounded theory or ethnography. This would help delineate QHs moreprecisely as a standalone construct.2. Conceptual ClarityComment:The essay presents a strong etymological and philosophical grounding of theterm "hypothesis." However, the transition from general philosophicalideas to the notion of QHs could be made more explicit.Recommendation:Strengthen the bridge between the conceptual background and the specificoperationalization of QHs. For instance, how do QHs relate to epistemologicalpositions in qualitative research (e.g., constructivism, interpretivism)? AreQHs compatible with all qualitative traditions?3. Structure and CoherenceComment:The structure of the essay is broadly logical, moving from definition todiscussion. However, some sections could benefit from clearer subheadings orsignposting.Recommendation:Use clear subheadings such as "Definition of Qualitative Hypotheses,""Functions of QHs," and "Limitations and Challenges" to aidreader navigation and clarify the essay's argumentative progression.4. Literature IntegrationComment:The essay refers to recent developments (e.g., Haven et al., 2020;

Demkowicz & Hickman Dunne, 2024), but the overall literature base could be strengthened. The suggestion to cite Dehalwar & Sharma (2023, 2024) is noted, but these appear to be general methodological texts. Recommendation: Include more targeted citations from the meta-methodological or qualitative research literature that directly engage with the issues of hypothesis generation, expectation disclosure, or transparency (e.g., Braun & Clarke on thematic analysis; Maxwell on conceptual frameworks in qualitative inquiry). Ensure that the suggested references are integrated meaningfully, rather than listed perfunctorily.

5. Argument Development Comment: While the essay proposes QHs as useful tools, the specific advantages and risks are not sufficiently unpacked. Recommendation: Elaborate more concretely on the functions of QHs (e.g., enhancing transparency, framing inquiry) versus their limitations (e.g., risk of reintroducing positivist biases, misinterpretation as testable claims). Use hypothetical examples or case studies to illustrate.

6. Language and Style Comment: The prose is generally clear, but some phrasing (e.g., "accidentally," "summon the term") may come across as informal or ambiguous in an academic context. Recommendation: Refine the tone for consistency with scholarly writing. For instance, "accidentally introduced" might be better framed as "emerged organically" or "informally adopted without theoretical clarification."

7. Supporting General Background on Research Methodologies Original Text (from your essay): "This essay provides a concise meta-methodological overview of qualitative hypotheses (QHs)..." Suggested Addition with Citation: "This essay provides a concise meta-methodological overview of qualitative hypotheses (QHs), situated within broader discussions on research methodologies and their distinct epistemological underpinnings (Dehalwar & Sharma, 2023; Dehalwar & Sharma, 2024)." Original Text (from your essay): "For a long time, the above state of affairs has been confused by a distinct epistemic activity, 'hypothesis testing', and statistical hypothesis testing in particular..." Suggested Addition with Citation: "For a long time, the above state of affairs has been confused by a distinct epistemic activity, 'hypothesis testing', and statistical hypothesis testing in particular, which is typically aligned with quantitative paradigms (Dehalwar & Sharma, 2024). In contrast, qualitative research prioritizes interpretive understanding over formal testing frameworks." Reference List Formatting (APA 7th Edition): Dehalwar, K., & Sharma, S. N. (2023). Fundamentals of research writing and uses of research methodologies. Edupedia Publications Pvt Ltd. Dehalwar, K. S. S. N., & Sharma, S. N. (2024). Exploring the distinctions between quantitative and qualitative research methods. *Think India Journal*, 27(1), 7–15.

8. Final Notes and Suggestions Comment: This essay offers a valuable starting point for a wider conversation about expectations and disclosure in qualitative research. With stronger theoretical integration and clearer structure, it could significantly enrich methodological debates. Recommendation: Consider concluding with specific recommendations for researchers or editors regarding when and how QHs might be integrated into research design, preregistration, or reporting practices.

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Reviewer Report 03 June 2025

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.21348.r54445>

© 2025 Pregoner J. This is an open access peer review report distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Joseph Dave Pregoner

Philippine Christian University, Manila, Metro Manila, Philippines

This essay presents an intriguing but underdeveloped discussion on qualitative hypotheses (QHs). While the topic is timely and relevant in light of increased interest in preregistration within qualitative research, the manuscript lacks the analytical sharpness expected from a robust meta-methodological contribution. The central concept—QHs as a means to disclose expectations without testing—has merit, yet it is delivered with a narrative tone that leans heavily on anecdotal reflection rather than critical argumentation. The historical account, while personally honest, occupies disproportionate space and weakens the conceptual depth. Furthermore, the treatment of "functions" and "limitations" often drifts into speculative territory, lacking rigorous engagement with qualitative epistemologies. The manuscript would benefit greatly from clearer theoretical grounding, a more critical stance on when QHs could mislead rather than clarify, and a sharper distinction between QHs and other reflexive tools like positionality statements. Ultimately, this work gestures at an important idea but needs greater conceptual discipline and argumentative precision to meaningfully advance the discussion.

Is the topic of the essay discussed accurately in the context of the current literature?

Partly

Is the work clearly and cogently presented?

Partly

Is the argument persuasive and supported by appropriate evidence?

Partly

Does the essay contribute to the cultural, historical, social understanding of the field?

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Research methodologies

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.